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The Duration of Civil Proceedings in the Italian Regions

It decreased by an average of 4.23%

Istat calculates the duration of civil proceedings in the Italian regions. The indicator is calculated as the effective average duration in days of the proceedings settled in the ordinary courts or civil sector - Sicid area net of the activity of the Guardianship Judge, the Preventive Technical Assessment on social security matters and from 2017 the Verbalisation of the sworn declaration . The data refers to the Italian regions in the period between 2012 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the duration of civil proceedings in the Italian regions in 2022. Basilicata is in first place by value of the duration of civil proceedings with a value of 861 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 751 units and Campania with a value of 627 units. Molise is in the middle of the table with a value of 425 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 421 units, and Tuscany with an amount of 385 units. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with a value of 232 units, followed by Piedmont with 218 units and Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount of 216 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in the value of the duration of civil proceedings between 2012 and 2022. Valle d'Aosta is in first place for the value of the duration of civil proceedings between 2012 and 2022 with a value of 169, 07% corresponding to a variation of 194 to 522 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a value equal to 53.64% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 151 units up to 262 units, and Piedmont with a variation equal to an amount of 6.86% corresponding to a variation from a value of 204 up to 218 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Molise with a value equal to -2.52% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 436 units up to 425 units, followed by Umbria with a variation equal to -2.86% corresponding to a variation from 454 up to 441 units and from Basilicata with a variation equal to -3.26% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 890 units up to 861 units. Liguria closes the ranking with a value of -23.50% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 349 units up to 267 units, followed by Emilia Romagna with a variation of -25.00% and Puglia with a variation equal to -31.45%. The average value of the duration of civil proceedings between 2012 and 2022 decreased by 4.23% in the Italian regions.

Italian macro-regions. The value of the duration of civil proceedings in the Italian macro-regions decreased in the North with a value equal to -5.88%, in the North-East with a value equal to -16.67%, in Central Italy with a value equal to -4.74%, in the South with a value equal to -12.34% and in the South with a value equal to -12.50%. However, there are some areas of the country in which the value of the duration of civil proceedings has grown and in particular in the North-West with a value equal to +2.85% and in the Islands with a value equal to 2.09% .

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Liguria, Piedmont, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Veneto, Trentino Alto Adige, Marche, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Abruzzo, Lazio, Umbria, Molise Sardinia;
- Cluster 2: Calabria, Puglia, Basilicata, Campania, Sicily.

From the point of view of the clusters we can note the following ordering: $C2 > C1$. We can note that the regions that make up cluster 2 are essentially southern regions. However, the regions of Cluster 2 do not exhaust the total number of southern regions. In fact, there are also southern regions that participate in Cluster 1, namely Molise, Sardinia and Abruzzo. A significant distinction is therefore proposed between some regions of Southern Italy and the remaining Italian regions.

Conclusions. The duration of judicial proceedings shows a general tendency towards reduction in all Italian regions and macro-regions in the observation period, i.e. between 2012 and 2022. On average among the Italian regions, the value of the duration of proceedings decreased by 4, 23%. However, there are also exceptions, i.e. regions and macro-regions in which the value of the duration of judicial proceedings has increased. These regions are: Valle d'Aosta, Trentino Alto Adige, Piedmont, Lombardy, Sicily, Sardinia. Among the macro-regions that have experienced an increase in the value of the duration of judicial proceedings are the North-West and the Islands. However, we can verify that the duration of judicial proceedings in Southern Italy tends to be 54.7% higher than in Central Italy, 139.23% in the North-East, 142.96% in the North, 142.96% in the North-West of 145.84%. We can therefore note the presence of a significant gap between North-South in the sense of the duration of judicial proceedings. The gap is such that on average a judicial proceeding in Southern Italy lasts around 1.7 years while in the North-West it takes around 0.7 years. It should be noted that the efficiency of the judicial system is generally considered a necessary characteristic for economic development and growth. Investors are attracted by the business opportunities that can be seized within legal and judicial systems that are able to protect and recognize private property rights and economic and political freedoms. Therefore, for a foreign investor, the fact of knowing that in the event of a dispute he will have to wait more than twice as long for the judgment in Southern Italy compared to the North-West, can be a significant disincentive to investment. Therefore, if the State intends to increase the attractiveness of the Italian economy, especially for foreign investors, then it should significantly improve its intervention in favor of a judicial system that is faster in resolving disputes to offer legal certainty to international operators.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

